

Study of diversity and human-herpetofauna interaction from the Chakothi, Hattian Bala, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

Pakistan is divided into three geographical units. Mountains and plateaus in the west, north, and northwest represent the coming together of three great mountain ranges: the Hindukush, Himalayas, and Karakorum. The data was collected from March, 2018 to February, 2020. The linear count method was utilized to assess amphibian and reptilian diversity. The questionnaire was utilized to examine the human and herpetofauna interaction. For the statistical analysis Shannon-wiener diversity (H') was analysis with the help of MS Word (2007). The aims of the research/study were to estimate the diversity of herpetofauna and the level of human-herpetofauna interaction in the study area. During the research noted that having 7 families, 15genus, 2 order, 20 species recorded from Hattian Bala. Shanon-weiner diversity index is as 1.23519. It is noted that Himalayan toad (*Bufo himalayanus*), Himalayan agama (*Laudakia himalayana*), Himalayan skink (*Scincella himalayana*), Bengal monitor (*Varanus bengalensis*), Striped Keelback (*Amphiesma stotatum*), rope-snake (*Ptyas mucosus mucosus*), Agror agama (*Laudakia agorensis*), Chekered Keelback (*Xenochrophis piscator piscator*), Blue rock Agama (*Laudakia tuberculata*) and Fat tail gecko (*Eublepharis macularius*) are recorded from the study area.

Keywords: Amphibian, Reptiles, Folklore, Ethnomedicine

Citation: Lal, R., N. Aziz. 2022. Study of diversity and human-herpetofauna interaction from the Chakothi, Hattian Bala, Pakistan. International Journal of Forest Sciences. 2: 1-7.

Received: January, 2022; **Accepted:** February, 2022

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan is divided into three geographical units. Mountains and plateaus in the west, north, and northwest represent the coming together of three great mountain ranges: the Hindukush, Himalayas, and Karakorum. The Hindukush, the Himalayas, and the Karakorum have some of the world's highest peaks; this mountainous landscape has had a significant impact on hydrology, geology and physiography; and it has an important role in the present time for the distribution and composition of organisms in the Indo-Pakistan region (Schaller, 1976; Khan, 2006).

It is one of the earliest divisions of the subcontinents, and it cradles a proof of 600 million years of solid waste washed down from the Himalayas. It serves as the Tethys Sea's forerunner. The vast top of the Himalayas is currently arranged by Punjab and Sind plains, a touching sharing of mountainous terrain and ground fauna

and vegetation (Khan, 2006). The vast terrain is definitely the Indus River's watershed. From the major physiographic property of plentiful grounds in Sind and Punjab, the Indus is its drainage sink. This vast area of land is primarily made up of alluvium that has been scrubbed down with Indus. It is Pakistan's most fruitful division. Initially, it is surrounded by vast pampas and tropical thorn trees (Khan, 2006).

Herpetology has never been a favorite field among Pakistani biologists, because lot of folklores are present about herpetofauna especially snake bites (Altaf, 2022). In India, however, there have been some active prominent herpetologists. Herpetology is a difficult subject in several Indian universities. The BNHS, which is well-known around the world and has a well-established journal and museum, encourages people to learn about reptiles and amphibians. The lack of interest among Pakistani zoologists is primarily owing to a lack of compensation and the lack of related resources. In the absence of a research institution, data on amphibians and reptiles can be collected and compared. To fill in some of the gaps, the author collaborated with Rahida Tasnim to publish field guides for chelonians and amphibians, and is currently working on snake and lizard guides. Check lists of Pakistan's chelonians, crocodilians, amphibians, snakes, and lizards have also been published. The herpetologist published about herpetology to make herpetology famous among native peoples (Wildlife of Pakistan). In addition, in 1993, a book on (Snakes of Pakistan) Sar Zameen-a-Pakistan kay saamp was published, and in 2000, a book on (Frogs and Lizards of Pakistan) Sar Zameen-a-Pakistan kay Mandak aur Khazanday was published. A handbook to the snakes of Pakistan was published in both German and English in 2002 (Khan, 2006). Parts of herptiles viz. fats (Ijaz and Faiz, 2021), venom (Altaf and Faiz, 2021), used in folk (Saleem *et al.*, 2021) and modern medicine (Alves *et al.*, 2009; Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2018; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Akhtar, 2021; Nazir, 2021; Habib, 2022).

The diversity of reptiles and amphibians is constantly threatened by the negative effects of urban development, which has resulted in fragmentation of the larger environment, agricultural growth, pollution, and altered natural climate patterns (Kamal and Faiz, 2022). Similarly, prohibited hunting and the use of reptile and amphibian body parts in medicine have resulted in the extinction of many species. The current study is thus planned with the following goals in mind: to estimate the diversity of herpetofauna in “Hattian Bala”, Pakistan and to assess the point of human-herpetofauna interaction in Hattian Bala.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The data was collected from March, 2018 to February, 2020.

STUDY AREA

The Indian-occupied Jammu and Kashmir's “Baramulla District” (Figure 1) and “Kupwara” border the “Hattian Bala” on the east and north, the “Muzaffarabad” on the west and the “Bagh” on the south and population of Hattian Bala is above 230,000 (The-Nation, 2017).

Figure 1: Map of the Hattian Bala, AJ&K.

STUDY OF AMPHIBIAN AND REPTILIAN DIVERSITY

The "linear count method" was used to assess the diversity of "amphibian and reptilian" species using "direct" and "indirect" counts. Physical presence and voices are included in the "direct count," while remains and meeting with local people are included in the "indirect count" as similar by other researchers (Altaf, 2016; Adil *et al.*, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021). The animals were observed with binoculars (32x50) and Khan (2006) was studied to correctly species identification.

STUDY OF HUMAN-HERPETOFAUNA INTERACTION

The Human-herpetofauna was analyzed through the questionnaire.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

“Shannon-wiener diversity index (H')” was analysis with the help of MS Word (2007).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Information gathered from male (110) and female (90) respondents, all are Muslims. Respondents Education from the study area is as; MA (20) BA (30), Matric (40), Primary (30), BA (30), Middle (40), and Illiterate (10). Respondents casts from the study area is as; Abbasi (60), Awan (40); Raja (30), Mughal (70).

Bala During the research noted that having 2 order, 7 families, 15 genera and 20 species recorded from Hattian Bala. Shannon-weiner Diversity index is as 1.23519. Himalayan toad (*Bufo himalayanus*) is collected from the study area with “relative abundance” as 0.037383 from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Himalayan agma (*Laudakia himayalayana*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.068536) from the chakothi, district Hattian Bala. North-Pakistan Agma (*Laudakia pakistanica*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.046729) from the Chakothi district Hattian Bala. Himalayan skink (*Scincella himalayana*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.062305) from Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Bengal monitor (*Varanus bengalensis*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.015576) from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bal. Striped Keelback (*Amphiesma stolatum*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.04) from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Rope-snake (*Ptyas mucosus mucosus*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.093458) from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Agror agama (*Laudakia agrorensis*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.040498) from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Chekered Keelback (*Xenochrophis piscator piscator*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.031153) from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Blue rock Agma (*Laudakia tuberculata*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.024922) from the Chakothi, district Hattian Bala. Fat tail gecko (*Eublepharis macularius*) is recorded from the study area (R.A. 0.071651) from the Chakothi, district Hattian (Table 1 and 2). Amphibian and reptiles’ diversity and distribution were also documented from Punjab (Adil *et al.*, 2020) and Azad Jammu and Kashmir (Haider and Faiz, 2020; Altaf *et al.*, 2021; Faiz and Farooq, 2021). Similar Findings are documented by other scientists (Khan, 2006; Jablonski *et al.*, 2019; Khan and Ahmad, 2019).

Table 1: The Classification of the herpetofauna of Hattian Bala, AJ&K.

Sr.	Scientific name	Common name	Species Authority	Order	Family
1	<i>Bufo himalayanus</i>	Himalayan toad	Gunther, 1864	Anura	Bufonidae
2	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	Oriental Garden Lizard	(Daudin,1802)	Squamata	Agamidae
3	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i>	Monitor lizard	Stoliczka, 1872	Squamata	Agamidae
4	<i>Laudakia himayalayana</i>	Himalayan agma	Steindachner, 1869		Agamidae
5	<i>Laudakia pakistanica pakistanica</i>	North-Pakistan Agma	Baig, 1989	Squamata	Agamidae
6	<i>Laudakia pakistanica khani</i>	North-Pakistan Agma	Baig and Bohme, 1996	Squamata	Agamidae
7	<i>Laudakia tuberculata</i>	Blue rock Agma	Hardwicke and Gray, 1827	Squamata	Agamidae
8	<i>Traplus agilis pakistanensis</i>	Brilliant ground agama	Rastegar-Pouyani, 1999	Squamata	Agamidae
9	<i>Eublepharis macularius</i>	Fat tail gecko	Blyth, 1854	Squamata	Eublepharidae

10	<i>Siwaligekko battalensis</i>	Reticulate plump-bodied gecko	Khan, 1993	Squamata	Gekkonidae
11	<i>Lacodon mackinnoni</i>	Mackinnon's Wolf Snake	Wall, 1906	Squamata	Colubridae
12	<i>Scincella himalayana</i>	Himalayan skink	Gunther, 1864	Squamata	Scinidae
13	<i>Varanus bengalesis</i>	Bengal monitor	Daudin, 1802	Squamata	Varanidae
14	<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i>	Striped Keelback	Linnaeus, 1758	Squamata	Colubridae
15	<i>Oligodon arnensis arnensis</i>	Banded kukri snake	Shaw, 1802	Squamata	Colubridae
16	<i>Naja oxiana</i>	Brown cobra	Eichwald 1837	Squamata	Elapidae
17	<i>Ptyas mucosus mucosus</i>	Rope-snake	Linnaeus, 1758	Squamata	Colubridae
18	<i>Spalerosophis diadema diadema</i>	Red spotted diadem snake	Schelegel, 1837	Squamata	Colubridae
19	<i>Xenochrophis piscator piscator</i>	Checkered Keelback	hneider, 1802	Squamata	Colubridae
20	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i>	Russell's chain viper	Shaw and Nodder, 1797	Squamata	Viperidae

Table 2: The Statistical analysis of the diversity of study area.

Sr.	Scientific name	Pi	Log Pi	PilogPi
1	<i>Bufo himalayanus</i>	0.037383	-1.42732	-0.05336
2	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	0.062305	-1.20548	-0.07511
3	<i>Laudakia agrorensis</i>	0.040498	-1.39256	-0.0564
4	<i>Laudakia himalayana</i>	0.068536	-1.16408	-0.07978
5	<i>Laudakia pakistanica pakistanica</i>	0.046729	-1.33041	-0.06217
6	<i>Laudakia pakistanica khani</i>	0.043614	-1.36038	-0.05933
7	<i>Laudakia tuberculata</i>	0.024922	-1.60342	-0.03996
8	<i>Traplus agilis pakistanensis</i>	0.062305	-1.20548	-0.07511
9	<i>Eublepharis macularius</i>	0.071651	-1.14478	-0.08202
10	<i>Siwaligekko battalensis</i>	0.024922	-1.60342	-0.03996
11	<i>Lacodon mackinnoni</i>	0.071651	-1.14478	-0.08202
12	<i>Scincella himalayana</i>	0.062305	-1.20548	-0.07511
13	<i>Varanus bengalesis</i>	0.015576	-1.80754	-0.02815
14	<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i>	0.093458	-1.02938	-0.0962
15	<i>Oligodon arnensis arnensis</i>	0.096573	-1.01514	-0.09804
16	<i>Naja oxiana</i>	0.096573	-1.01514	-0.09804
17	<i>Ptyas mucosus mucosus</i>	0.021807	-1.66141	-0.03623
18	<i>Spalerosophis diadema diadema</i>	0.018692	-1.72835	-0.03231
19	<i>Xenochrophis piscator piscator</i>	0.031153	-1.50651	-0.04693

20	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i>	0.009346	-2.02938	-0.01897
Total				-1.23519

During the survey noted that 3 species of herptiles used in folk medicine as fat of *Bufo himalayanus* is used against bacteria. Fat of *Eublepharis macularius* is used against cancer. Venom of *Daboia russelii russelii* is used against snake bite, cancer (Table 3). Similar findings were documented by other researchers (Mendonça *et al.*, 2014; Shrestha and Gurung, 2019; Altaf *et al.*, 2020; Saleem *et al.*, 2021; Umair *et al.*, 2022).

Table 3: Ethno-herpetofauna of the study area.

Sr.	Species	Application/ Product	Diseases	Respondents
1	<i>Bufo himalayanus</i>	Topical/Fat	Antibacterial	1
2	<i>Eublepharis macularius</i>	Topical/Fat	Cancer	7
3	<i>Daboia russelii russelii</i>	Topical/Venom	Snake bite, cancer	3

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